

DELIVERABLE

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Table of Content

Table of Content	3
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
Chapter 1: Theoretical aspects of the optics	5
1.1 The sorter reformulated	5
1.2 Point misalignment	7
1.3 Oversimplified model	8
1.4 Numerical model	9
1.5 Lateral coherence	11
1.6 Scanning problems	12
1.7 Chromatic aberration	14
2. Experimental tests and comparison with data	16
2.1 Chromatic aberration Early tests	16
2.2 Chromatic aberration: improved tests	17
3. Ideas for preliminary experiments	20
3.1 Theory of OAM spectrum	20
3.2 Experiments	21
4. Setup and Simulation of EMCD experiments	21
4.2 Theory	24
4.3 Simulation results	27
4.4 Feasibility	32
Annex 1: Referee	34
ANNEX 2: References	36
ANNEX 3: ABBREVIATIONS:	38
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	38

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable contains the first conclusions about the viability of electron magnetic chiral dichroism (EMCD) experiments, as the acquisition of atomic-scale EMCD is one of the main goals of the Project.

In preparation for the actual EMCD measurement, a large comprehensive theoretical and experimental-test work was found out to be necessary. Such work focused on both the modified electron optics as well as on the interaction between probe electrons and sample and is described in this deliverable.

The planned EMCD measurement was thus proven to be feasible and will be effected as part of T4.4. This won't be a problem since the theoretical work thus carried out also proved that the out-of-focus approach planned for T4.4 is not necessary and actually risk being counter-productive (see sect. 4.4 in the text). T4.2 and T4.4 should be looked at as one big macro task anyway.

This deliverable is thus propaedeutic to the final deliverable D4.4 "manuscript of paper on EMCD" although some of the technical development exposed here are fundamental also for plasmon experiments (D4.3) and for Cryo-experiments (D5.4).

In this deliverable we first check the role of aberrations and of other experimental limits on the acquisition of OAM spectra in scanning mode and in coincidence with EELS spectra. Then we discuss the measurement proper:

The acquisition of a reliable EMCD spectrum is by itself a very complicated operation as it requires that all parts of the microscope work correctly. For this reason, we have highlighted all intermediate experiments, simulations, and calibrations preliminary to the final EMCD measurement.

Based on the considerations and results of this deliverable, we conclude that the acquisition of OAM-EELS experiment is not far away.

The deliverable is divided into 4 main chapters. The first chapter is mainly devoted to the calculation of the limits of the electron optics that still hampers the acquisition of the OAM spectra scanning mode and with energy filtering.

In the second one, we report on the preliminary experiments performed to verify the operative condition of the microscope and the comparison with the above calculations.

The third chapter concerns the additional step of OAM-EELS experiments that aim to verify the operation of the full spectroscopy system. If successful this experiment would have an interest on its own as a very important application of the OAM sorter.

The fourth and final chapter contains the detailed EMCD simulation accounting for the dynamic scattering in a crystal. This last step is fundamental also to assert the degree of localization of the wavefunction at the exit of the crystal as this results to be the main parameter for the feasibility of the measurement.

Finally, the conclusions summarize the results and contain a discussion on the feasibility of the measurement.

Chapter 1: Theoretical aspects of the optics

1.1 The sorter reformulated

In order to evaluate possible limitations in the use of the OAM sorter, we reformulated the sorter theory in a compact form based on the complex formalism. The main goal consists in being able to consider the effect of small misalignments and the aberrations of the optic system on the final OAM resolution.

Fig 1: scheme of the sorting apparatus.

In the complex formalism usual in optics and electron optics, each point is indicated by a single complex number $z=x+iy$. In this respect, the transformation of coordinates of an ideal sorter is written as:

$$Z' = s \ln(z) = X' + iY' \quad (1)$$

Where s is the scale factor (a real number) of the transformation .

In fact for a given z , $|z|$ is the distance from the optical axis and $\varphi = \arg(z)$ is the azimuthal angle in the plane.

The transformation in eq. 1 is therefore written as $\ln(z) = \ln(|z| \exp(i\theta)) = \ln(|z|) + i\theta$.

This written in the usual formalism is

$$\begin{aligned} X' &= s \ln(\sqrt{x^2 + y^2}) \\ Y' &= s \operatorname{atan}(y, x) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

In figure 1 the scheme of the sorting apparatus is described using the convention that u_x are the positions in the different planes and u_x' are the related angles.

The scheme refers to the condition for a STEM-SORTER experiment with a convergent beam focused in the sample plane. The objective lens has a focal f_0 and the effective focal distance between sorter 1 and sorter2 is denoted by f . In most practical cases f is not obtained by a real lens but it is the effect of the convergence (with curvature $1/r$) of the beam and the focal of the objective lens:

$$\frac{1}{f} = \frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{f_0} \quad (3)$$

If the sorter1 was a simple aperture of size u_1 the diffraction would correspond to an angle of

$$u'_1 = -\frac{u_1}{f} \quad (4)$$

But since the aperture has a structured phase the diffraction is not a point but an extended wave whose width is dictated by the sorter transformation

$$\Delta u'_1 = s \ln(u_1) \quad (5)$$

In facts the actual form of the physical sorter1 is

$$\varphi = s u \ln(u) - s u \quad (6)$$

And therefore the tilts are just $t_{x,y} = \left(\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial y} \right) = (s \cdot \ln(u)) \vec{x} + s \theta \vec{y}$.

Eq 5 is found for $u = u_1$. For the typical conditions we use in experiments s , and therefore the tilt, is of the order of $3\mu\text{rad}$.

Using equation 5 we end up with an angle of the external diffraction point (see in red in figure)

$$u'_2 = u'_1 + \Delta u'_1 = s \ln(u_1) - u_1/f \quad (7)$$

That transforms into a real space position

$$u_2 = u_1 + f \Delta u'_2 = s f \ln(u_1) \quad (8)$$

In the angle direction corresponding to y the real extension is indeed $u_2 = 3\mu\text{rad} \cdot 0.5 \text{ m} \cdot 2\pi = 10\mu\text{m}$ (the imaginary part of $\ln(u)$ ranges between 0 and 2π) as in real experiments.

Thus sorter 1 transformed the beam from a circular distribution $x_1=r \cos(\theta)$, $y_1=r \sin(\theta)$ at the plane of sorter 1 to a rectangular patch $x_2=s f \ln(r)$, $y_2= s f \theta$ at the plane of sorter 2. The OAM of an electron manifests itself in a phase variation $\Psi(r, \theta)=\ell \theta$ at sorter 1 and hence a linear phase gradient $\Psi(x_2, y_2)=\ell y_2/(s f)$ at sorter 2. This linear phase gradient induces a beam deflection $\alpha = \lambda (d\Psi/dy_2)/(2 \pi) = \lambda \ell/(2 \pi s f)$ which is proportional to the OAM. The essence of the OAM sorter is to employ this deflection to create the desired OAM spectrum. However, because this deflection is much smaller than the tilts u_2' present in the beam entering sorter 2, we first have to adjust the tilts u_2' such that they do not have effect in the plane of the OAM spectrum. Therefore, we make sorter 2 such that it adjusts u_2' such that all electrons seem to originate from a single point at sorter 1.

Thus we can enforce the condition that the angle after sorter 2 is

$$u_3' = -u_3/f$$

and since $u_3 = u_2 = s f \ln(u_1)$,

$$u_3' = s \ln(u_1)$$

So the sorter2 must add a tilt $\Delta u_2'$ such that

$$u_3' = u_2' + \Delta u_2' = -\frac{u_1}{f} + s \ln(u_1) + \Delta u_2' \quad (9)$$

From which we calculate the final tilt after sorter 2

$$\Delta u_2' = \frac{u_1}{f} = \frac{1}{f} e^{\frac{u_2}{sf}} \quad (10)$$

It is easy to confirm that, in this complex formalism, this is correspondent of the Sorter2 phase effect.

The actual change of direction corresponding to an OAM of $1\hbar$

$$\alpha = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi s f} = \frac{\lambda}{u_2} \quad (11)$$

For our experiment this angle is 0.2 μrad . Back extrapolating the beam to the S1 plane we find that the corresponding change of complex position is $d = f\alpha = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi s} = 100 \text{ nm}$

1.2 Point misalignment

Let's assume now that the sorter2 and the diffraction of sorter1 are misaligned by δu_2 . The angle at the exit of sorter2 becomes

$$\Delta u_2' = \frac{1}{f} e^{\frac{u_2 + \delta u_2}{sf}} = \frac{1}{f} e^{\frac{u_2}{sf}} \cdot e^{\frac{\delta u_2}{sf}} = \frac{u_1}{f} \left(1 + \frac{\delta u_2}{sf} + \dots \right) \quad (12)$$

where the additional term $\Delta u'_3 = \frac{u_1 \delta u_2}{sf^2}$ describe the effect of the misalignment.

$$u'_3 = -\frac{u_1}{f} + s \ln(u_1) + \frac{u_1}{f} \left(1 + \frac{\delta u_2}{sf} + \dots\right) = s \ln(u_1) + \frac{u_1 \delta u_2}{sf^2} + \dots \equiv s \ln(u_1) + \Delta u'_3 \quad (13)$$

The effect of the extra angle $\Delta u'_3$ can be traced back to the sorter1 plan as

$$\Delta d = f \Delta u'_3 = \frac{u_1 \Delta u_2}{sf} \quad (14)$$

The relative variation of the alignment and therefore the OAM resolution loss is

$$\frac{\Delta d}{d} = \frac{\frac{u_1 \Delta u_2}{sf}}{\frac{\lambda}{2\pi s}} = \frac{2\pi u_1 \Delta u_2}{\lambda f} \quad (15)$$

For a working OAM spectrometer $\Delta d/d < 1$ namely $\Delta u_2 < \frac{\lambda f}{2\pi u_1}$ this typically means something like 15 nm in the sorter2 plane.

This leads us to a first important conclusion: the alignment of the two elements of the sorter is crucial to the correct functioning of the device, especially considering that the critical value of 15 nm of misalignment is typically less than the drift of the aperture on a long term.

Moreover, this effect is even stronger in sample position.

Let's assume that the beam, at the sample position, is the incoherent superposition of two waves originating from two sources. This can happen for example for the nature of the inelastic scattering or for the lateral incoherence (source size effect). If we assume that the sorter is tuned for the first source, how big can be Δu_0 namely the distance of the second source ?

Since the SAD and the sample position are conjugated with a magnification given by the ratio of the focals f an f_0 the minimal allowed distance is related to Δu_2 by

$$\Delta u_2 = \frac{f}{f_0} \Delta u_0 \quad (16)$$

Depending on the ratio between the two focals, this can even be smaller than 0.15 nm. This problem can potentially hamper many incoherent applications, but fortunately there can be solutions.

1.3 Oversimplified model

There is an even simpler explanation to why a small position indetermination produces a blurring of OAM

Fig 2: Phase difference in the objective aperture plane between to point sources located at a distance d .

When two point sources at the sample position are separated by d (Fig 2) they produce a phase difference in the objective aperture plane by

$$\delta z = \frac{d}{f_0} \alpha f_0 \rightarrow \delta \phi = \frac{d}{\lambda} \alpha \quad (17)$$

f being the focal and α the convergence. That can be also expressed as a function of the elastic diffraction limited resolution d_{res}

$$\delta \phi \approx \frac{d}{d_{res}} \quad (18)$$

When $\delta \phi$ is much larger than π the OAM decomposition gets confused. In practice for the sorter to work we need the incoherent delocalization to be lower than elastic delocalization, namely the diffraction limited size of the coherent probe.

1.4 Numerical model

We implemented a numerical method to simulate the OAM spectroscopy experiment based on full wave calculation and free space propagation able to quantitatively describe the effects of several kind of aberrations/misalignments on the final resolution.

We will consider a system composed of the two sorter elements and two lenses (the objective lens and a diffracting lens). The different sizes and distances are reported in Fig 3.

Fig 3: the experimental set-up. The distances between the different plane are reported, as well as the focal of the lenses and the main physical parameters. Notice the change of nomenclature with respect to fig 1. $f_0 \rightarrow f_1$ $f \rightarrow D_2$.

The beam is free space propagated between the elements using the Fresnel-Kirchhoff integral:

$$\psi_z(u, v) = \frac{e^{ikz}}{i\lambda z} \iint \psi_0(x, y) e^{-ik\frac{xu+yv}{z}} dx dy \quad (19)$$

The main limitation of the approach is dictated by the very high sampling required in order to describe the phase of the lenses: mathematically a lens is described by the complex function $\Psi_L = e^{i\frac{\pi r^2}{f\lambda}}$; in order to correctly compute the lensing effect the phase shouldn't vary too fast, in any case the phase difference between adjacent pixels must be less than π .

$$\frac{d\phi}{dn} < \pi \quad (20)$$

According to this criterion, assuming the wavefunction to be sampled over a square mesh grid of 8192x8192 point (the maximum allowed on a PC), the minimum focal distance we can use is:

$$f_{min} = \frac{L^2}{\lambda n} \approx 198 \text{ mm} \quad (21)$$

Therefore, it is not possible to numerically simulate the objective lens, which has a focal distance of 3.3 mm. To overcome this limitation we will assume plane wave illumination on the objective lens and an equivalent focal equal to the distance to sorter2 ($D=500\text{mm}$).

A test run of the simulation, performed with a perfect alignment is reported in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Amplitude of the wave function in different planes.

1.5 Lateral coherence

The models discussed at paragraphs 1.2 and 1.3 make clear that if the waves are emitted from point sources at a distance d even of 1\AA this is sufficient to completely blur the OAM spectrum because the phase on the sorter is not univocally well defined.

It turns out that a typical probe is affected by a naturally occurring incoherence that is inherited by the finite source size. In a Schottky FEG the source is typically some nm and gets de-magnified to get a very tiny probe. The parameters that control this are mainly two: gun lens and spot size. For High resolution STEM probes spot size is 9 (in FEI nomenclature) and the typical source size effect are 0.5\AA on the sample of course more detailed estimation depends on the full setting.

In these conditions the source size is typically just below the threshold for reducing the OAM resolution. We carried out experiment with spot size 7 (less source de-magnification, with a spot size of roughly 0.2 nm) and found indeed a net detriment of the OAM resolution.

This means that all experiments must be carried out with spot size 9.

For the inelastic scattering the problem could be more complicated because of delocalization. This aspect for EMCD will be discussed in par 4.4.

1.6 Scanning problems

Scanning the beam over the sample is also a potential source of problems since every shift of the beam position produces a large mis-alignment of the two sorter elements. In facts, even in atomic resolution STEM the scanned area is much larger than the limit of 0.15 nm that we previously calculated in section 1.2.

On the other hand it is very important to be able to scan the beam as the EMCD requires a quite accurate positioning on the atomic column.

Thermo-Fisher microscopes offer a very convenient solution to this problem. It is indeed possible to use and align some special coils whose effect is to compensate the shift effect in the lower part of microscope, as depicted in Fig 5.

The alignment of these coils is not very common but we could operate it in our setup.

Fig 5: Schematic representation of the descan coils.

Fig 6 shows a series of OAM spectra acquired in different beam positions.

In general, we scanned the beam over a squared area with 50 nm side and the OAM spectrum looked relatively stable with slight variations mainly due to the specimen. Notice that if the de-scanning coils were deactivated, the spectrum would be completely lost in every point different from the initial position.

It must be noted that even if the compensation were as good as compensating 99% of the shift the shift would be still 5\AA . In other words the scheme works better for very small areas or for very accurate compensations. Still this should be sufficient for an atomic resolution map of about $10 \times 10 \text{ nm}$.

Fig 6: series of OAM spectra acquired during the scan at different distances (see labels) from the perfect alignment condition obtained thanks to the descan coils. The spectrum appears to be only mildly distorted.

1.7 Chromatic aberration

A first approach to the description of chromatic effect would be to start from the disk of confusion of chromatic effect and assume a delocalization of the same size.

However this appears as an overestimation of chromatic. The chromatic effects can be simulated by summing over many defocuses. The defocus is therefore not the same as changing the position, the probe is much less affected by small focal changes and has its own width often comparable with the defocal effect. In any case without an explicit simulation the result could be wrong.

So we decided to make a full simulation of the lens system as in par 1.4 and fig 3 accounting for defocus effects. The focal length of a lens vary linearly with the acceleration voltage:

$$df_1 = C_c \frac{dE}{E_0} \approx f_1 \frac{dE}{E_0} \quad (22)$$

Where C_c denotes the chromatic aberration of the objective lens. A defocus df at the sample plane becomes on the sorter2 plane:

$$df_1 = f_1 \frac{dE}{E_0} M^2 = \frac{dE D_2^2}{E_0 f_1} \quad (23)$$

Where M is the magnification in the sorter 2 plane $M = D_2/f \approx 150$.

Therefore the equivalent focal length from Sorter 1 to sorter 2 becomes:

$$f_{eff} = D_2 + \frac{D_2^2 dE}{f_1 E_0} = D_2 \left(1 + \frac{D_2 dE}{f_1 E_0} \right) \quad (24)$$

The chromatic effect of the diffraction lens is instead:

$$f_D = f_2 \left(1 + \frac{dE}{E_0} \right) \quad (25)$$

Finally, chromatic effects of the sorters elements have been also accounted for in the phases of the 2 electrostatic sorters:

$$\varphi_1(E) = \left(1 + \frac{\Delta C_E}{C_E}\right) \varphi_1(E_0) \quad \text{and} \quad \varphi_2(E) = \left(1 + \frac{\Delta C_E}{C_E}\right) \varphi_2(E_0) \quad (26)$$

And also in the wavelength dependence in eq. 19. These effects are negligible compared to the chromaticity of the lenses.

We can now simulate the energy loss: as expected the beam is no longer on focus in the sorter2 plane and starts to bend, shrink and shift (Fig 7). These effects hamper the correcting effect of sorter2.

Fig 7: Numerical simulations of the effect of the chromatic aberration on the diffraction of sorter1 for different values of the energy loss (see labels).

However, an energy loss of several tens of eV is required in order to obtain an observable effect on the shape of the beam.

In a similar fashion, the final OAM spectrum is only slightly affected by the chromaticity of the system (Fig 8). Furthermore the main effect of the defocus take place in the radial direction, orthogonal to the OAM spectrum itself.

Fig 8: numerical simulations of the effect of the chromatic aberration on the final OAM spectrum for different values of the energy loss (see labels).

Based on these simulations we can conclude that the chromatic effect for a perfectly aligned microscope should not be a limiting factor in the EMCD experiment.

2. Experimental tests and comparison with data

2.1 Chromatic aberration Early tests

We made a first series of experiments necessary for the calibration of the possible problem of the GIF (Gatan Image Filter). We used a non-standard alignment of the projection system in order to rotate the OAM spectrum in the direction orthogonal to the energy dispersion.

In this way, on the GIF camera, the OAM should be in the vertical direction while the energy in the horizontal. We used the graphene sample to have a controllable known spectrum. The convergence was set to 2mrad and the spectrometer was aligned in the standard image mode (before the GIF) to a resolution of $1.5 \hbar$ (in some cases $1.3 \hbar$). Unfortunately what we found can be summarized in Fig 9

The OAM spectrum even at 0 loss was quite broad but most problematic is that the OAM resolution decreases with the energy loss.

The broadening can only partly be evaluated since the entrance aperture of the GIF seems to limit the actual broadening that would otherwise spread even further.

Fig 9. top left: recorded double dispersed OAM (vertical axis)-EL (horizontal axis) spectrum. **Bottom left:** intensity line profile along the OAM axis for different energy loss values. **Right:** FWHM of the Gaussian fit of the line profiles as a function of the energy loss.

A fit of the FWHM of the spectrum indicates that the broadening has a linear dependency with the energy loss. This points directly to a chromatic aberration related effect that is indeed proportional to energy and that would reflect, more or less, linearly in a broadening.

However the numerical simulation indicated that the loss of resolution due to chromatic effect should have been much smaller (see 1.7).

It was difficult to single out the cause of this discrepancy. However during these experiments, we experienced miss-functioning of the GIF filter that eventually led to a complete failure of the device.

2.2 Chromatic aberration: improved tests

In a more recent experiment we wanted to carry out a second series of experiments to check the discrepancy between simulations and experiments.

In this case, since the GIF filter was down, we used a different strategy.

We took advantage of a separate (and little known) command in the Titan control software to change the microscope acceleration voltage. Using this command we changed the energy by δ up to 100eV. The resulting OAM spectrum is shown in Fig 10. This gives two important results. The first result that appears evident is that there is perfect match between simulation and experiment.

Fig 10: experimental OAM spectrum obtained for different beam energies. The corresponding numerical simulation is reported as inset.

And in both experiments and simulations the change by even 100eV in energy corresponds to a mild deformation of the spectrum.

According to our observation the decisive factor introducing the huge chromatic effect was the misalignment of the microscope. A correct centering along the optical axis with the classic HT wobbler procedure made for a huge improvement.

It is of course natural to perform such procedure but it is still impressive how big the effect is. Most probably we are dealing with a sort of Chromatic coma that is enhanced by the slightly off centered geometry that is typical of the OAM sorter.

In addition we must stress that we did not have the possibility to check the GIF and its effect on the OAM spectrum.

In fact the idea of a OAM dispersion orthogonal to the energy dispersion requires an imaging capacity in the vertical direction but normally this is not well aligned in a GIF (especially the relatively old one in Titan HOLO). We cannot be sure that this relatively old GIF allows for a focused imaging in this direction.

These tests thus confirmed that we won't have any chromatic aberration problems provided the microscope is correctly aligned.

2.3 Filter effect

It is possible that the energy filter itself introduces a further deformation of the spectrum that hampers the acquisition. So we made a further comparison between a normal OAM spectrum acquisition (top panel of Fig 11) and the OAM spectrum acquired through the filter (bottom panel of Fig 11)

Fig 11: Comparison of the OAM spectrum in standard operation mode and with the energy dispersion on the GIF spectrometer. In fig a the OAM dispersion is in the y direction while P_r (radial momentum) is dispersed in the x direction. In fig c the P_r dispersion is completely averaged out while the x scale is the Energy.

In both cases the OAM dispersion is in the vertical direction. In the case above the horizontal scale is related to the radial momentum while in the lower case the horizontal axis is the energy.

However when an average is carried on in the horizontal direction the OAM dispersion remains similar with a main resolution loss due to the MTF of the CCD (unfortunately the magnification was small) and the spectrum was sampled on a few pixel. In a later work indeed we used the microscope XL lens to obtain a further magnification of the spectrum but we could not test this with the GIF since it was broken.

It must be noticed that even if there is no sample the OAM spectrum is not monochromatic. The additional oscillations are due to an imperfect alignment of the sorter and can be reduced in future with the use of automatic alignment procedure.

3. Ideas for preliminary experiments

3.1 Theory of OAM spectrum

The experiments should in principle concentrate on dichroism. However the energy of the $L_{2,3}$ edges of the Fe that are typically used in EMCD experiments are at about 710 -720 eV. This means that the signal is typically very low. Moreover we will see that the dichroic signal is very difficult to verify considering the limitation of the present form of the OAM sorter.

Therefore we consider here the possibility of using the OAM -EELS dispersion for a simpler demonstration of the use of our configuration.

Fig 12 shows indeed the advantage of the OAM sorter in the application to 2D anisotropic materials (h-BN, graphene, ...). According to simulations, based on the symmetry of the projected density of states (ρ DOS) as implemented in the standard DFT methods, the combined OAM-EELS spectra should show a distinct difference between $1s \rightarrow \sigma$ ($\ell = -1, +1$) and $1s \rightarrow \pi$ ($\ell = 0$) transitions in C-K edge. In this case the advantage of the sorter is to allow for a direct separation of the two contributions in a single acquisition, while normally this would require a tilt of the specimen in the standard (q, E) basis to separate the two overlapping features, which may be not possible in the experimental setup.

Fig 12: (a) Calculated π and σ components in the C-K edge spectrum in hexagonal graphite or graphene, and (b) double dispersion OAM-EELS from a [001] oriented crystal, in which the two components are directly separated in the $\ell = 0$ and $\ell = \pm 1$ channels.

3.2 Experiments

Having addressed the correction of chromatic effects (see section 2.2), we were unable to acquire new spectra because the GIF spectrometer was down. This rare and unforeseen event delayed our planned measurements until recently. Once the GIF had finally been repaired, we could not perform the experiments due to the COVID-19 emergency. We plan to execute them as soon as the COVID-19 emergency is over.

4. Setup and Simulation of EMCD experiments

This section is almost exactly taken by the recent paper E. Rotunno et al Orbital angular momentum resolved electron magnetic chiral dichroism Physical Review B 100 (22), 224409.

Additional information can be gained through M Zanfrognini et al. arXiv preprint arXiv:1911.02006 that we don't report here.

The equation in this section are numbered separately from the rest of the paper a1,a2 ...

4.1 Introduction

We describe here the aimed EMCD experiment and a series of simulations aimed at finding the best conditions to perform it.

The core of EMCD is the measure of the asymmetry in the transition probability in the EELS scattering of core-loss edges (typically the L edge of transition metals) as a function of the exchange of orbital angular momentum (OAM).

The presence of a magnetization in the material introduces a different spin population in different energy levels and therefore the above asymmetry and is very indicative of the magnetism of the material.

The XMCD is the very similar technique but uses X-ray polarization of absorbed photons instead of the exchange of the electron OAM.

While controlling X-ray polarization is quite feasible, controlling the OAM of electrons has been for long time a complicated matter.

In the the early formulation of EMCD proposed by Schattschneider et al.[1], the observation of a dichroic signal requires working with a parallel beam in a two (or three) beam condition, obtained through a tilt of the crystal about a zone axis and collecting the inelastically scattered electrons at two specific positions in the diffraction plane after the sample. The main drawbacks to this approach are a limited spatial resolution[2] (of the order of 10 nm), a poor signal to noise ratio and a strong dependence of the

strength of the dichroic signal from the sample thickness: concerning this point, as shown in Ref[1] through numerical simulations, for certain thicknesses the expected EMCD signal turns out to be negligible, despite the magnetization of the material under study. For these reasons, EMCD experiments have been among the most difficult in TEM.

The breakthrough in this field has been the introduction of electron vortex beams in electron microscopy[3][4][5] and the possibility to produce atomic size electron vortices[6][7]. Specifically, electron beams with a given topological charge, passing through an isolated atom, can induce atomic transitions in which the magnetic quantum number (at least in dipolar approximation) is changed of a quantity $\Delta m = \pm 1$ [8]. Focusing, for example, on the case of $2p \rightarrow 3d$ transitions in magnetic transition metals, we expect to have differences in energy resolved diffraction patterns measured for two vortices with opposite orbital angular momentum (OAM) $\pm \hbar$, because of the different population of the spin-up and spin-down 3d electronic states. This apparently feasible approach presents however a series of difficulties.

Firstly, it requires performing two measurements using opposite electron vortex beams (typically $l = +1$ and $l = -1$ vortex) that cannot be precisely performed in the same point, due to the unavoidable sample and probe drift. This strongly affects the reliability of the differential measurement implied in EMCD.

Secondly, while propagating in the crystal, an electron vortex does not conserve its OAM as the free space cylindrical symmetry is broken by the crystal potential: this point has been widely investigated through multislice simulations[9], for example in Ref.[10][11][12]. Practically this means that the probing electrons in the crystal are not in a quantum mechanical state with defined OAM along their propagation direction, so parts of beam intensity acquire different OAM, reducing intensity of $\pm \hbar$ components and, in turn, the achievable dichroic signal[13].

Finally, they feature a nearly zero intensity in their centre where the atomic column should be located, therefore the intensity can be easily predicted to be small.

These drawbacks can be solved if a post selection in terms of OAM is performed on the inelastically scattered electrons, as firstly proposed in Ref.[14] in the case of amorphous materials.

In QSORT we propose a new way of performing EMCD experiments based on a post-selection in terms of both energy and OAM of the inelastically scattered electrons from a crystalline magnetic sample. The proposed experimental setup is reported in Fig 13. A conventional STEM probe defined by a circular aperture is used to image a magnetic sample along a high symmetry zone axis; two phase elements (called OAM sorters)[15] [16] [17] are then introduced in the microscope column at the objective and select area diffraction planes and enable to spatially separate the OAM components of the electron beam. With an appropriate orientation of these elements, the electrons can be then analyzed through an energy spectrometer, so that a double dispersion (in orthogonal directions) in both energy and OAM of the electrons is finally obtained[18].

Fig 13. Proposed experimental setup needed to perform an OAM resolved EELS experiment.

This experimental setup offers several advantages over previous propositions of EMCD experiment. Differently from the use of a vortex beam as a probe, this technique permits to obtain the two spectra needed for the EMCD measurements simultaneously, without modifying the features of the probing electrons. The sample is oriented along a high symmetry direction, allowing for in-plane atomic resolution.

Moreover, as we will outline in the following, such an approach also increases the experimental signal to noise ratio, as a large fraction of the overall inelastic signal is effectively used to obtain the EMCD spectra, differently from the original approach of Ref [2].

4.2 Theory

In the following we will describe the theory necessary to simulate the OAM resolved core loss spectra $I(l, \Delta E)$ in crystalline samples by means of multislice calculations and point out how the formalism required to describe EMCD spectra becomes clearer once a description in terms of electronic OAM is preferred with respect to one in terms of their linear momentum. The influence of finite resolution in both energy and OAM of the experimental apparatus over the OAM resolved EELS spectra is also analyzed.

The combined action of the OAM sorters and the energy spectrometer provides experimentally the quantities

$$I(l, \Delta E) = \text{Tr}[\hat{\rho}_f \hat{P}_{lE}] \quad (\text{a1})$$

where $\hat{\rho}_f$ is electron density matrix after passing through the sample, $\hat{P}_{lE} = \int dk |l, k, E\rangle \langle l, k, E|$ and $E = E_0 - \Delta E$ is the energy of an electron which has lost an energy ΔE in the interaction with the sample: the quantum states $|l, k, E\rangle$ are characterized by a defined OAM $\hbar l$ and an energy E , while k is a quantum number related to the radial degree of freedom whose physical meaning will be clarified in the following sections. The quantity $I(l, \Delta E)$, experimentally available with the proposed set up, defines the number of electrons that have an energy $E_0 - \Delta E$ and are found in a state with OAM equal to $\hbar l$: therefore the dichroic signal can now be obtained as a difference between $I(+1, \Delta E)$ and $I(-1, \Delta E)$: because of what said before, an unbalance in intensity between these two functions should be observed.

Here we follow the approach presented in [19] to simulate OAM resolved core loss spectra. This procedure (here reviewed for completeness) relies on a series of reasonable approximations i.e.

- we assume the electrons experience only a single inelastic process while passing through the crystal, a valid hypothesis because of low probability of core excitations;
- the energy of the probing electrons is assumed equal to 300 KeV, so we work in paraxial approximation, for which the electronic wavefunction can be written as $\Psi(\mathbf{r}) = e^{ik_z z} \phi(\mathbf{r}^\perp; z)$, where the following definition will be used in the following $\phi(\mathbf{r}^\perp; z) \equiv \langle \mathbf{r}^\perp | \phi_z \rangle$ for the transverse wavefunction in a plane at defined z ;
- we use z -locality approximation [20] [21], where the state of an electron after inelastic scattering at an atom located at position z_a can be written as $|\phi_{z=z_a}^{fa}\rangle = i\sigma \hat{V}_{i \rightarrow f}^{\text{proj}} |\phi_{z=z_a}^{\text{el}}\rangle$. In this process the atom at z_a experiences a transition $|i\rangle \rightarrow |f\rangle$, $|\phi_{z=z_a}^{\text{el}}\rangle$ is the state of the electron at $z = z_a$ before the inelastic scattering process, $\hat{V}_{i \rightarrow f}^{\text{proj}}$ is defined as in Eq.4 of [19] and σ is a parameter only depending on the energy of the incoming beam.
- we consider here the case of a highly symmetric cubic crystal, i.e. bcc iron: as we will outline in the following, this assumption will simplify the definitions of the quantities of interest, even if the conclusions obtained for this system can be straightforwardly generalized to less symmetric samples.

We now define $I(l, \Delta E)$ as

$$I(l, \Delta E) = \int_0^{K_{\text{Max}}} I(l, k, \Delta E) dk \quad (\text{a2})$$

where

$$I(l, k, \Delta E) = \sum_{a,f} \left| \langle l, k | \phi_{z=z_a}^{f,a} \rangle \right|^2 \delta(\Delta E + \varepsilon_f - \varepsilon_i) \quad (\text{a3})$$

The states $|l, k\rangle$ are defined such that $\langle r^\perp | l, k \rangle = e^{il\varphi} J_{|l|}(k|r^\perp|)$, i.e. they correspond to Bessel beams with orbital angular momentum l and transverse wavevector k . The integral over k in Eq.(2) is performed up to $K_{\text{Max}} = \alpha/\lambda$, where α is the semi-collection angle of the OAM sorters while λ is the electron de Broglie wavelength, here fixed to 1.97 pm: such a parameter needs to be optimized to maximize the strength of the dichroic signal.

It is possible to rewrite $I(l, k, \Delta E)$ as

$$I(l, k, \Delta E) = \sigma^2 \sum_a \int dk_1 \dots \int dk_4 D^*(k_1; l, k) C(k_2) D(k_3; l, k) C^*(k_4) \frac{S_a(\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}', \Delta E)}{\tilde{q}^2 \tilde{q}'^2} e^{i(q-q')a} \quad (\text{a4})$$

where the sum over a is performed over the atomic positions at which the inelastic process of interest can occur; $D(k_1; l, k)$ is the 3D Fourier transformed elastically scattered Bessel beam with topological charge l , transverse wavevector k and energy $E_0 - \Delta E$ propagating from the bottom side to the top of the crystal: in its expression, we neglect the energetic dependency of D , as in the following we will focus on a small energy range of energy losses ΔE in the interval $[\Delta E_{\text{min}}, \Delta E_{\text{max}}] = [690, 750] \text{eV}$; the propagation of an electron with energy $E_0 - \Delta E_{\text{min}}$ is analogous to the one of an electron with energy $E_0 - \Delta E_{\text{max}}$, because $E_0 \gg \Delta E_{\text{max}}, \Delta E_{\text{min}}$.

Analogously, $C(k_2)$ is the three dimensional Fourier transform of the incident beam elastically propagating in the material with energy E_0 ; both $D(k_1; l, k)$ and $C(k_2)$ have been computed performing the 3D Fourier transform of the wavefunction inside the crystal, computed by a multislice calculation. Furthermore, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{q} &= k_1^\perp - k_2^\perp + q_{\Delta E} \hat{z} \tilde{q}' = k_3^\perp - k_4^\perp + q_{\Delta E} \hat{z} \\ q &= k_1 - k_2 q' = k_3 - k_4 \\ q_{\Delta E} &= k_z^f - k_z^i \end{aligned}$$

In Eq.(4) $S_a(\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}', \Delta E)$ is the atomic mixed dynamic form factor (MDFF) [22], which provides the energy dependence of $I(l, k, \Delta E)$: working within dipolar approximation we can rewrite [23]

$$S_a(\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}', \Delta E) = \tilde{q} N_a(\Delta E) \tilde{q}' + i M_a(\Delta E) [\tilde{q} \times \tilde{q}']$$

where $\mathcal{M}_a(\Delta E)$ is a vector containing the magnetic properties of the sample, while $\mathbb{N}_a(\Delta E)$ is a real symmetric tensor keeping into account the non magnetic contributions to the overall signal. In the following we will suppose the magnetic field of the objective lens to be sufficiently strong to saturate the sample magnetization along z , so only the z component of $\mathcal{M}_a(\Delta E)$ will be taken different from zero. At the same time we assume to work with a cubic crystal having cell axes parallel to \hat{x} , \hat{y} and \hat{z} , for which $\mathbb{N}_a(\Delta E)$ becomes a diagonal tensor with all the diagonal element equal one to the other.

We now introduce a set of functions [24] which enable us to group together the different terms associated to the dynamical diffraction effects: practically we define

$$Q_a^i(l, k) = \sigma \int dk_1 \int dk_2 D^*(k_1; l, k) C(k_2) \frac{\hat{q}_i}{q^2} \quad i = x, y, z \quad (\text{a5})$$

$$X_i(l, k) = \sum_a |Q_a^i(l, k)|^2 \quad (\text{a6})$$

$$S(l, k) = 2\text{Im}[\sum_a Q_a^x(l, k) Q_a^y(l, k)^*] \quad (\text{a7})$$

So we have

$$I(l, k, \Delta E) = \sum_{i=x,y,z} N_i(\Delta E) X_i(l, k) + \mathcal{M}(\Delta E) S(l, k) \quad (\text{a8})$$

where we have neglected the dependence of \mathbb{N} and \mathcal{M} from the atom type as we will focus on the energy losses produced by atoms of the same type and with the same coordination geometry in the crystal: the functions $X_i(l, k)$ and $S(l, k)$ describe the effect of the dynamical diffraction of the electrons in the crystal and are the parameters which need to be tuned to get the optimal experimental conditions.

Exploiting the crystal cubic symmetry, we can define a relative dichroism function at fixed k as:

$$R(\Delta E, k) = 100 \cdot \frac{\mathcal{M}(\Delta E)}{N(\Delta E)} \frac{|S(l, k)|}{\sum_i X_i(l, k)} \approx 25 * \frac{|S(l, k)|}{\sum_i X_i(l, k)}$$

The ratio $\frac{\mathcal{M}(\Delta E)}{N(\Delta E)}$ depends on the electronic structure of the particular material and should be calculated via DFT calculation, but for strong ferromagnets it is typically close to 0.25,[25] and represents the maximum expected dichroic signal from the experiment.

In order to relate the previously defined functions to the quantities we expect to measure experimentally, we have to integrate equation (8) in the interval $[0; K_{\text{Max}}]$: under rather general assumptions and using the definitions provided in Eq.(6) and Eq.(7) it is possible to show that $X_i(l, k) = X_i(-l, k)$ and $S(l, k) = -S(-l, k)$, so by integration over k we find:

$$I(l, K_{\text{Max}}, \Delta E) = N(\Delta E) \sum_{i=x,y,z} X_i(l, K_{\text{Max}}) + \mathcal{M}(\Delta E) S(l, K_{\text{Max}}) \quad (\text{a9})$$

So fixing on the cases $l = \pm 1$, we derive

$$I(+1, \Delta E; K_{\text{Max}}) - I(-1, \Delta E, K_{\text{Max}}) = 2\mathcal{M}(\Delta E) |S(+1, K_{\text{Max}})|$$

and

$$I(+1, \Delta E, K_{\text{Max}}) + I(-1, \Delta E, K_{\text{Max}}) = 2 \sum_i N_i(\Delta E) X_i(+1, K_{\text{Max}})$$

from which we can define the dichroism function as

$$D(\Delta E; K_{\text{Max}}) = 100 \cdot \frac{\mathcal{M}(\Delta E) |S(+1, K_{\text{Max}})|}{\max[N(\Delta E) \sum_i X_i(+1, K_{\text{Max}})]} \quad (\text{a10})$$

This function effectively describes the strength of the dichroic signal and it depends on the semi collection angle chosen to perform the experiment.

In the following we will present the behavior of the functions defined in the last paragraphs and we will outline a possible strategy to select an appropriate value for the experimental semi collection angle.

4.3 Simulation results

In this section we present the trends of the non-magnetic $X_i(l, k)$ and magnetic $S(l, k)$ signals calculated for $l = [-2:2]$ and for different values of k , considering the simple case of bcc iron, with TEM optical axis along the 001 direction. In the simulations we have considered an orthogonal supercell with size of $[20 \times 20 \times 140]a$ ($a = 2.87 \text{ \AA}$ the iron lattice parameter), i.e. an overall sample thickness of 40 nm. The STEM probe is characterized by a semi-convergence angle of 7.3 mrad and it is centered on the Fe column at (0,0). The coefficients $X_i(l, k)$ and $S(l, k)$ have been evaluated by summing the products $D^*(k_1; l, k)C(k_2)$ through a modified version of the software MATSv2 [24] using a convergence parameter of $5 \cdot 10^{-9}$.

In Fig. 14a) the magnetic part $S(l, k)$ is displayed for different values of l : firstly we point out that this function computed for $l = +1$ is equal in modulus but opposite in sign to the one evaluated for the opposite topological charge and it turns out to be null if the orbital angular momentum is taken equal to zero; furthermore, this magnetic part becomes negligible for larger $|l|$ (as one can realize from the functions evaluated for $l = \pm 2$), making the electrons collected for $l = \pm 1$ good candidates to get information about the magnetic properties of the sample under study.

In Fig. 14b) we present the non-magnetic term given by $\sum_i X_i(l, k)$, which is non zero also for the $l = 0$ case: it decreases more rapidly than the non-magnetic contribution associated with $l = \pm 1$ and it is peaked at smaller scattering angles (λk). Differently from the magnetic terms, these quantities are independent from the sign of the OAM (as we have $\sum_i X_i(1, k) = \sum_i X_i(-1, k)$) while they exhibit a decreasing strength with increasing the value of $|l|$.

Fig. 14: Trends of the magnetic term $S(l, k)$ (a) and non-magnetic term $\sum_i X_i(l, k)$ (b) for l in the interval $[-2; +2]$ as functions of the transverse wavevector length k . c) Behavior of the relative dichroic function $R(\Delta E, k)$ as functions of the scattering angle λk d) Figure of merit function (defined in Eq.11 of the main text) introduced to define an optimal value for the maximum semi collection angle in order to maximize the magnetic signal.

In Fig. 14c we show the relative dichroic function $R(\Delta E, k)$ evaluated for $l = -1$ in the λk interval $[0 ; 20]$ mrad. This function assumes value well above 15% in the entire detection interval, approaching the theoretical limit of 25% for scattering angle exceeding 5 mrad.

These trends point out the need of properly choosing the semi collection angle in a real experiment in order to maximize the detected magnetic signal. Our target is now to define a figure of merit function which can indicate a value of K_{Max} for which the magnetic contribution (at a given $l = \pm 1$) is maximized with respect to the non-magnetic one, while taking into account that an increase of the overall semi collection angle decreases the experimental signal to noise ratio (SNR), making this experimental configurations less advantageous.

A reasonable figure of merit could be given by [26][27]:

$$F(K_{Max}) = \frac{1}{K_{Max}} \frac{|S(l, K_{Max})|}{\sqrt{\sum_i X_i(l, K_{Max})}} \quad (a11)$$

where the ratio between the magnetic and the non-magnetic terms is analogous to the SNR function provided by Ref [28], identifying the magnetic contribution as the “signal” we would like to optimize and

$\sum_i X_i(|l|, K_{\text{Max}})$ as the “noise” to be decreased; at the same time, the function $1/K_{\text{Max}}$ describes the increase of the experimental SNR we expect to observe enlarging the semi collection angle [27]. In case considered in these calculations, this function (shown in Fig. 2d) exhibits maximum values in the range [5; 7] mrad, denoting these angles as the appropriate semi collection angle to be used in experiments on this material. Another important point is to understand if the approach outlined in this work is able to give access to the magnetic properties of the sample with lateral atomic resolution: in fact looking at the definition of $S(l, k)$ in Eq.7, we notice that the sum is performed over all the magnetic atoms in the sample, in principle not only those of the column on which the STEM probe is focused, as one should have to obtain atomically resolved magnetic maps of the material under study.

To clarify this point, we have evaluated the contributes to the magnetic (Fig. 3a and 3c) and non-magnetic signals (Fig. 3b and 3d) for $l = +1$ of both the atoms of the column on which the probe is centered and of those in the neighboring columns [24] [28]. The magnitudes of the terms is represented as a solid sphere centered on the each atomic position. The radius of each sphere is directly proportional to the module of the represented term. The same information is also encoded in the spheres’ color in logarithmic scale (see color bars in figure 3).

It is immediate to show that the contribution of the atoms to these terms decreases exponentially while considering atoms not on the column centered in the origin. These results guarantee that the measured signal comes almost entirely from the atomic column of interest, so that a lateral atomic resolution in measuring the material magnetic properties is effectively expected.

Fig. 15: a) and c) 2D and 3D views of the contribution to the function $S(+1, \lambda K_{\text{Max}} = 7 \text{ mrad})$ of atoms close and on the atomic column on which the electron STEM probe is centered: each atom is surrounded by a sphere whose radius (and color, in logarithmic scale) is proportional to the strength of the contribute of that atom: notice that by increasing the distance from the atomic column in (0,0) we observe an exponential decrease of the contribution of the atoms to S. b) and d) Analogous analysis for the non-magnetic part of the signal.

Once the functions describing the dynamical diffraction of the electron beam in the sample are known we can estimate the OAM resolved energy loss spectra using Eq.9: the functions $N(\Delta E)$ and $\mathcal{M}(\Delta E)$ have been evaluated through first principles calculations [1][28], while the maximum collection angle has been fixed to 7 mrad; First principles calculations of bcc iron were performed using the WIEN2k package [29] using generalized gradient approximation of exchange-correlation functional [30]. Spin-orbital coupling effects were included. The atomic sphere radius of iron was set to 2.33 Bohr radii, the basis size cut-off was $RK_{\text{max}}=8.0$ and Brillouin zone integrations were performed using modified tetrahedron method with 10000 k-points. The resulting spectra, for different OAM, are presented in the upper panel of Fig. 4a while in the lower portion of this figure we show the dichroic function defined in Eq. (10). It is immediate to observe that the quantity $D(\Delta E; \lambda K_{\text{Max}} = 7 \text{ mrad})$ reaches values of about 15% (or more) at both the L2 and the L3 iron edges, a quantity much larger than the relative dichroic signal normally observed with conventional approaches to EMCD.

As outlined in the first part of this work, the presented measure should give access to a double dispersion in both energy and orbital angular momentum, in perpendicular directions: in reality the spectra shown in *a* are different from those we expect to measure.

To obtain results similar to those expected from a real-life experiment, we have to include in our treatment the broadening in energy of the electron beam (which is not perfectly monochromatic) together with the finite energy resolution of the OAM sorters. In practice, what we expect to observe experimentally is

$$\Gamma(l, \Delta E) = I(l, \Delta E) \otimes f(l, \Delta E) \quad (\text{a12})$$

where $f(l, \Delta E)$ is given by the product of two gaussian functions describing the broadening introduced by the experimental set up. Notice that here the OAM is treated as a continuous variable as the sorter can transform a vortex with topological charge l in a spot centered at a coordinate C_l [15][16] [17] with lateral extension equal to $C\Delta l$ (C is a constant dependent on the features on constitutive sorter parameters: for simplicity in the images presented in the main text this quantity has been taken equal to 1). The result of this convolution procedure is presented in Fig. 3b, where we have taken $\Delta l = 0.5\hbar$ and $\Delta E = 0.7\text{eV}$, being this the resolution expected using the sorter in a fan-out configuration like the one recently demonstrated for optical sorters [31][32]. Notice that despite the finite OAM resolution which introduces a partial mixing of the signal at $l = 0$ with the one for $l = \pm 1$, a strong asymmetry between $\Gamma(+1, \Delta E)$ and $\Gamma(-1, \Delta E)$ is expected to be clearly observable.

Fig. 16: a) Upper panel: OAM resolved EEL spectra computed for l in the range $[-2; +2]$, assuming a collection angle of 7 mrad. Lower panel: function $D(\Delta E)$ defined in Eq. 10; notice that the dichroism strength reaches values of about 18% both in correspondence of the L2 and the L3 edge of Iron. b) Convolution of the spectra shown in a) with the product of two Gaussian functions ($\Delta l = 0.5\hbar$) describing the broadening in OAM and in energy introduced by the OAM sorters and by the non monochromaticity of the electron beam.

Finally, in Fig. 17 we present the in plane spatial mapping of the function $D(\Delta E; \lambda K_{\text{Max}} = 7 \text{ mrad})$, obtained computing the OAM resolved EEL spectra following the procedure outlined before, but scanning the STEM probe on different points on the sample: in Fig. 5a (b) the function is computed in correspondence of the L2 edge (L3 edge), at energy $\Delta E = 720 \text{ eV}$ ($\Delta E = 708 \text{ eV}$).

It is immediate to notice that, in absolute value, the strength of the relative dichroism is maximum once the electron beam is centered on an atomic column, for both the two edges, while it decreases of 6-7 % once the probe is moved in between two columns: this contrast in OAM and energy filtered images gives information about the magnetic properties of the sample with atomic lateral resolution.

Fig. 17. Spatial mapping of the function $D(\Delta E; \lambda K_{\text{Max}} = 7 \text{ mrad})$ computed for the iron L2 (a) and L3 (b) edges. The finite contrast in the images can give access to an atomically resolved mapping of the sample magnetic properties.

4.4 Feasibility

The above simulations indicate that the sorter-based EMCD measurement is still feasible in spite of the limitations of the EELS+sorter experiments. The simulations also specify which are the right conditions to successfully do these measurements

The two main problems that potentially affect the measurement are the delocalization of inelastically-scattered electrons (briefly touched upon in sect. 1.5) and their limited collection angle.

As for delocalization, in a general EELS experiment the scattering occurs through the excitation of an internal degree of freedom of the specimen. This implies a partial “measurement” of the electron beam and therefore a loss of coherence. Every electron loss is characterized by a different level of incoherence. The excitation of plasmons for example produces a strong delocalization in real space but a small one in momentum space. On the other hand, the excitation of core electronic levels, as in EMCD, is strongly characterized by a localization of the wavefunction.

In practice, after a core excitation the electron can be described as a spherical wave departing from a small area.

In general, the area would probably be still too large for a sorting measurement (see sect. 1.5). In fact in old, normal EMCD, where the zone axis of the sample has got to be tilted with respect to the beam axis, there is transverse coherence at least over a couple of nanometers. However, in our case the zone axis

of the sample is parallel to the beam axis: under these conditions, the calculations above indicate that the channelling takes care of laterally confining most of the probe and of the scattered intensity within the single column of atoms, with a resolution that is better than that of the electro-optical system.

This means that, after channeling, the delocalized sources of inelastic scattering very much look like our probe – a condition that needs to be satisfied for the sorter to work (see sect. 1.3), since the subsequent objective lens transforms the spherical waves emerging from the sample into plane waves with which the sorter is design to work. This is therefore a very convenient approach. On the other hand, the approach that instead was planned for T4.4 is counterproductive, because working under Fresnel conditions in this case would mean that the sorter is fed spherical waves and therefore would not work properly. (Contrast this with the case of plasmon excitations in the sample, which instead produce near-planar exit waves in the electron beam and therefore are better suited for this Fresnel approach.)

This means that task T4.4 will be completely devoted to the experimental realization of what was here theoretically calculated and simulated, using the present Fraunhofer-like configuration

A slightly different approach is necessary for the graphene case that is typically a 2D material and is thus less affected by channeling.

For this kind of sample it will be necessary to perform experiments at very small convergence or (better) to post-select a small angle in the final state.

Another experiment could be based on putting the graphene sample in the condenser changing completely the geometry of the scattering.

As for the collection angle, there is a trade-off between optimal S/N and the risk of incurring into aberrations due to being too much off-axis. In particular, the above simulations show that the collection angle should ideally cover a range up to 7 mrad, since when collecting over a wider angle the favourable contribution to S/N ratio tends to be less significant. While early experiments could only cover a range up to 2 mrad, we have now tested longer Sorter1 needles that worked already well up to 4.5mrad and should still perform reasonably well up to 6 mrad. If we were limited to this angle, still the S/N ratio would be in an acceptable range of more than 10%.

Finally, the result will be more reliable if the OAM sorter is slightly improved by reducing the side bands in the OAM spectrum, which are due to the non-perfect alignment (see graph below).

Fig. 18 Experimental example of a spectrum taken in vacuum with about the best background condition so far.

The OAM spectrum of vacuum collected here (uncalibrated) shows that the main peak contains only roughly 50% of the signal. This is the best result so far but can be further improved by working on the alignment.

This can only be done by working automatically with automated TEM control on many parameters and this is what we are working on at the moment.

Further specific improvements that have already been put in place are the 6 electrodes version of sorter1 and the anti-contamination heater briefly described in D5.4.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion even if we could not make the final EMCD acquisition or the simplified experiment on graphene we have afforded all technical problems, potential issues and typical feasibility questions of the experiment and the experiment seems to be feasible.

We are approaching the condition where we understand every single parameter and only we need a working apparatus and appropriate time.

Annex 1: Referee

Note: We have asked our referee to skip the details of chapter 4 since the paper has been already peer refereed.

Referee1

The paper is very long and informative, full of ideas and physics. I think there is still material for 2 technical papers apart from the main EMCD results. In particular I am very surprised that the complex formalism works also for the sorter.

In this regards it is not so clear to me why we cannot use the disc of confusion of chromatic effect and assume each point as incoherent?

This has been a very controversial in our discussion. It turns out the amplitude of the displacement in the sorter 2 plane is correctly predicted but the displacement is somehow less effective as it deforms but does not shift the diffraction of sorter1 (see fig. 8).

Second question is how general is the case of carbon experiments. If I correctly understand there are many transitions that would benefit from the OAM sorter.

To observe differences in the OAM spectra for $l = 0$ and $l = \pm 1$ (in dipolar approximation and not considering EMCD) an anisotropy in the bonds in the plane (x, y) with respect to the z -direction is needed in the final state. The K-edge of all anisotropic materials is a clear case. Another possibility could be the separation of d -orbitals in transition metals L edges due to octahedral vs. tetrahedral vs. planar symmetry, but this is complicated by the crystal field splitting. In general, we expect the OAM sorter to give similar results as for q orientation-dependent EELS measurements, but with the advantage of a single acquisition. Beyond dipolar approximation, the OAM sorter can be further used to separate the initial state, for instance, the L1 edge ($l = 0$ initial core state) from the L2,3 edge ($l = 1$ initial core state) in transition metals.

Referee2

This deliverable reports on OAM resolved EMCD experiments.

It is divided in two parts: the first one is dedicated to detailed discussion on the feasibility of the experiments from an electron optical point of view. In particular, the effect of the lateral and temporal coherence of the electron beam after interaction with the sample are deeply discussed together with the alignment of the diffraction from sorter1 with the devices of sorter2.

The second part, already published is a theoretical discussion on the possibility to obtain atomic resolved EMCD maps thanks to the OAM sorter.

The experimental part of the deliverable shows some interesting results on the effects of the energy loss on the quality of the OAM spectra and the possibility to obtain OAM vs EELS spectra on the CCD of the GIF.

Unfortunately some technical problems on the GIF impired the possibility to obtain the final experimental results.

I have two questions on the simulation part:

-pag 9 of the deliverable: it is claimed that “in practice for the sorter to work we need the incoherent delocalization to be lower than elastic delocalization.” The elastic delocalization should be defined.

Done

-The numerical simulation of the electron wave function are carried out neglecting the effect of the objective lens for computational reasons. The authors should explain why this approximation does not influence the comparison with the experimental configuration.

In practice in the experiment we end up using collection angles up to 7 mrad exactly to avoid the problem of the aberration. However since this microscope has also an aberration correction it could be in principle possible to correct the aberration. In real experiments we actually prefer to put Cs-corrector off in order to have a longer value of f .

ANNEX 2: References

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ANNEX 3: ABBREVIATIONS:

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd. - UK	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics - IT	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Inst	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL

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